

*Algerian women's cultural awareness of the importance of sports and their
attitudes toward practicing them
Practice A Field Study of Some Fitness Halls in Sétif*

Berroudj kamel

*University of Mohamed Lamine Debaghine, Setif 2. Laboratory of Physical Activity
Sciences, Sports, and Public Health ; k.berroudj@univ-setif2.dz*

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Abstract

The study aimed to identify the culture of attitude towards practicing physical and sports activities for Algerian women in light of some variables. The researcher used the descriptive approach on a sample consisting of 60 women practicing sports activities. The researcher used a scale of attitudes towards physical activities. The results of the study found that there are no differences in the culture of attitude towards practicing physical and sports activities for women due to the variables of gender and educational level.

Corresponding author: **Berroudj kamel**
e-mail: k.berroudj@univ-setif2.dz

1. Introduction

Sport for all is a term with significant meaning, implying that sports are no longer exclusive to men and adults but have expanded to include all segments of society, both young and old, men and women. This is due to the benefits of sports for individuals in various aspects. As Hani and Ismail (2014) mention, "Engaging in physical activity contributes to improving individual health, achieving good posture, and enhancing physical fitness. It also improves the efficiency of the body's functional systems and positively impacts the psychological, mental, and social aspects of an individual, thereby positively affecting an individual's lifestyle both at work and at rest" (Abdullah Marzouq, Hadi Al-Sharif, and Badr Al-Khalaf, 2019, p. 3). This was also confirmed by the American Heart Association in 1992, which stated that a lack of physical activity increases the risk of various diseases (Hadadi Rahma et al., 2023, p. 520)

Therefore, sports must be accessible to everyone, men and women, young and old. This is emphasized in the International Charter issued by UNESCO in 1978, which states that the actual implementation of human rights is linked to the possibility of developing and maintaining each individual's physical, intellectual, moral, and spiritual abilities freely. Thus, the practice of sports should be guaranteed for both males and females in any society (Brahimi, 2019, p. 52).

There are many studies that have addressed the topic of women and sports from various perspectives. Among these are the study by Zahaf Mohammed (2015) and the study by Ghalami Iman (2015), which discussed women's participation in sports from cultural and social perspectives. Additionally, the study by Hanaa Abdullah Marzouq and others (2019) focused on psychological and health aspects. There have also been numerous international and national conferences that discussed women and sports, including the Seventh International Symposium on Women and Sports : Challenges and Opportunities held in M'sila, and a national symposium titled "The Reality and Prospects of Women's Sports in Algeria".

The social approach to sports, according to (Al-Jabour 2012)'s perspective, views that the topic of women and sports cannot be separated from men's sports. It is not logical to have a sports sociology specific to men and another sports sociology specific to women (Sisawi and Yassef, 2021, p.

125). Therefore, according to the researcher's point of view, there is currently no difference between the practice of sports for women or men. With the increase in various pressures and tasks assigned to women, both inside and outside the home, caring for their health through raising their awareness and health culture has become an inevitable necessity and a main goal. In fact, it is an effective strategy to reduce the spread of psychological, physical, and mental diseases with all their material and moral costs. Therefore, the World Health Organization seeks to stimulate the promotion of beneficial dietary systems and physical activity for women, because changing behaviors will bring future benefits to their health. (Dryas Laila and Mazouz Barkou, 2019, p. 282)

With technological advancement, the abundance of social media platforms, women's liberation from some constraints imposed by customs and traditions, and the opening of fitness centers, all these circumstances have significantly contributed to most women engaging in various types of sports regardless of age or educational level.

Physical activities and sports were rejected and unwelcome in past years for women in Algerian society due to the customs and traditions governing society, and the lack of widespread cultural awareness about the importance of sports practice. Add to that the shortage of sports facilities designated for women, which were exclusively for men. However, with technological development and the widespread cultural awareness among women, along with the opening of women-only fitness centers, we must not forget the significant role of social media sites and television programs in motivating women to practice sports activities in fitness centers.

Based on the previous results and taking into account the customs and traditions of Algerian women, the aim of this study is to identify the differences in women's attitudes towards engaging in physical and sports activities according to the variables of age and educational level.

1.1. Literature Review

Culture : It refers to the various knowledge, customs, and traditions that characterize the behavior of an individual or a group in society or the environment.

Attitude : It is an emotional state of an individual formed through a certain idea or topic that leads to a change in the individual's positions.

Physical Sports Activity : It encompasses various physical and sports activities and movements that an individual engages in to develop physical, psychological, health, and social aspects.

2. Method and Materials

2.1 Participants

The researcher employs a descriptive method to align with the study's objectives.

Sample and Selection Methods The sample was randomly selected and consisted of 60 women who engage in physical and sports activities at fitness centers in Setif, Algeria.

Study Scope Spatial Scope : Several fitness centers in Setif, Algeria.
Temporal Scope : From February 2024 to March 2024.

2.2. Materials

Research/Study Procedures **Kenyon Attitudes Scale:** The scale, originally developed by Gerald Kenyon and adapted into Arabic by Mohamed Hassan Alaoui, consists of 54 items across 6 dimensions:

Physical activity as a social experience, Physical activity for health and fitness, Physical activity as stress and risk experience, Physical activity as aesthetic experience , Physical activity for stress reduction, Physical activity as an experience of athletic excellence.

Scale Correction Method : The scale is corrected by observing the placement of the check mark (X) corresponding to the respondent's opinion with the assigned score, in accordance with the hypotheses. After completing the estimation of each statement, the total scale score and the score for each dimension corresponding to one of the hypotheses are calculated.

Scale Scoring Method : This scale follows a scoring method based on the positivity or negativity of the statements. Positive statements are scored (5, 4, 3, 2, 1) in order of positivity, while negative statements are scored (1, 2, 3, 4, 5) in order of negativity.

Table (1) illustrates the dimensions and scores for both positive and negative statements.

Dimensions	Positive Statements	Negative Statements
Physical activity as an experience of excellence	11, 17, 20, 25, 29	19, 39, 49
Physical activity for health and fitness	4, 10, 15, 18, 23, 32, 40, 4	6, 27, 36
Physical activity as an experience of tension and risk	7, 28, 42, 50, 53	1, 13, 22, 38
Physical activity as an aesthetic experience	3, 8, 14, 30, 33, 35, 41, 45, 48	/
Physical activity for stress reduction	12, 16, 21, 26, 37, 44, 51	31, 54
Physical activity for athletic excellence	2, 9, 34, 43	5, 24, 46, 52

2.3 Statistical Analysis

Statistical review was conducted using statistical software. The statistical methods used in our study include: mean, standard deviation, and t-test, All statistical analyses were performed with SPSS 23

3. Results

Table (2) illustrates the differences in Algerian women's attitudes towards physical and sports activities attributed to the variable of age.

Scale	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F Value	p Value
Total Score for the Scale	Between Groups	2,092	2	1,04	0,07	0,92
	Within Groups	1014,908	57	13,18		Not Significant
	Total	1017,000	59			

Note : p-value ≤ 0.05 indicates statistical significance

Table (2) indicates that there are no significant differences in the culture of women's attitudes towards practicing physical and sports activities attributable to the age variable. In attitudes towards practicing sports activities, where the calculated F anova value was 0.07 and its statistical significance P was 0.92.

Discussion:

It is clear from the table that the differences between the averages of cultural attitudes of women towards practicing physical and sports activities did not reach the level of statistical significance according to the age variable, as the F anova value was greater than the level of significance. Therefore, there are no differences in the attitudes of women towards engaging in physical sports activities for the sample studied that can be attributed to the age variable

The researcher attributes the results of this study to the spread of sports culture among various segments of society despite the difference in age. However, all women try to maintain their health and fitness. Personal freedom for women also plays an important role in their practice of various sports activities. This is due to the openness of society and breaking the fear of customs and traditions.

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The researcher also observed that women of various ages have started to practicing in different types of physical and sports activities by adopting a healthy lifestyle from psychological, physical, or nutritional aspects. This is done through following training and dietary programs to improve health behavior. This is facilitated by allocating specific times for women to practice sports in fitness centers away from mixed-gender environments, which has contributed to the level of inclination towards various types of sports activities.

It is observed that many studies focus on the nature of the female body and how it differs from the male body. As mentioned by (Melhem 1999), cited in (Abdul Hadi Shtiw 2017), a woman's body contains an amount of

fat reaching up to 23% of her weight, and that she is more susceptible to obesity. This is due to the lack of physical activities and spending long periods at home (Amira Abdul Hadi Shtiwi, 2017, p. 79).

Social media also plays an important role in promoting a culture of physical activity among women. Additionally, there are many fitness centers dedicated to women's sports practice to improve their fitness and achieve an ideal body, which positively impacts their psychological well-being (Belkoushi and Karrama, 2022, p. 944).

The results of this study align with those of Oudban Hamza et al. (2016), who found positive attitudes towards physical and sports activities among female students. Similarly, the results are consistent with those of Samia Hassan Al-Qattan et al. (2015), which found no differences in the reasons related to capabilities, psychological, administrative, and social factors motivating female athletes to engage in sports activities across different age groups (Samia Hassan Al-Qattan et al., 2015, p. 38).

However, the results of this study differ from those of Eman Galni (2015), which found that the negative view of society imposes a rejection of sports practice by families. They also differ from the findings of Ahmed Boujattat (2017), who concluded that age affects the inclination towards physical and sports activities. Furthermore, the results contrast with those of Hamida Qasdi (2013), which found differences in the significance of various dimensions of women's attitudes towards physical and sports activities according to age.

Table (3) illustrates the differences in Algerian women's attitudes towards physical and sports activities attributed to the variable of Educational level.

Scale	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F Value	p Value
Total Score for the Scale	Between Groups	10.62	2	5.31	0.40	Not Significant
	Within Groups	1006.37	57	13.07		
	Total	1017.00	59			

Note: p-value ≤ 0.05 indicates statistical significance

Table number (3) indicates that there are no significant differences in the cultural attitudes of women towards physical and sports activities attributed

to the variable of educational level. In the scale of attitudes towards sports activities, the calculated F value for the dimension of physical activity as a social experience was 0.40, with a statistical significance of P 0.66

Discussion:

It is clear from the table that the differences between the means of women's cultural attitudes towards physical and sports activities did not reach the level of statistical significance according to the age variable in all dimensions. The F value was greater than the significance level, indicating that there are no differences in the attitudes of women towards physical and sports activities for the research sample attributed to the educational level variable.

The researcher attributes the results of this study to the fact that all women, regardless of their educational level, engage in sports to maintain their mental, psychological, and physical health. According to Coakley, as cited by Anouar Al-Khouli (1993), one of the factors contributing to the advancement of women's sports is the focus on physical fitness (Sislawi and Yasf, 2021, p. 128). Additionally, technological advancements and social media, along with visual media, have increased the culture of women participating in physical and sports activities through programs available on social media networks or morning sports programs. The results of Hamadi and Amraoui's (2020) study found that media coverage plays an important and positive role in promoting and building the sports movement, especially women's sports.

The researcher also believes that women's inclination towards practicing in sports activities, despite differences in educational levels, is due to the positive psychological effects that sports have on women by alleviating their stress. A study by Landers, Rethorst, and Wipfli (2009) indicates that exercise helps reduce anxiety and depression and increases feelings of happiness due to the release of hormones such as endorphins and serotonin. This is a significant reason that motivates women to engage in sports (Hanaa Abdullah Marzouk et al., 2019, p. 26).

"The researcher attributes the results of this study, despite the different educational levels, to the fact that women are inclined to engage in sports activities in fitness centers because the strategic location of the state of Setif

and the modern culture in the society of Setif city have significantly contributed to promoting the culture of sports practice."

"The results of this study agree with the findings of the study by (Abdel Hadi Chitawi, 2017), which concluded that there are no differences in women's engagement in sports activities attributable to the educational level variable. However, the results of this study differ from the findings of the study by (Suleiman Lawsin, 2019), which found that there is a relationship between cultural level and female students' attitudes towards engaging in physical sports activities."

4. Conclusion

In conclusion of this research, we attempted to address one of the emotional aspects affecting women's participation in physical and sports activities. The nature of positive attitudes towards engaging in physical and sports activities has positive impacts on women from psychological, physical, social, and health perspectives. This research also concluded that there are several factors influencing the formation and change of attitudes for individuals in general and women in particular. This study aimed to understand the culture of sports practice among women according to some surrounding variables.

Therefore, it is essential to spread awareness and culture among women about the importance of engaging in physical and sports activities for psychological and health benefits. It is also necessary to continue promoting positive attitudes towards women's participation in sports activities, with a particular focus on health-oriented sports. This has significant importance for women at all stages. Additionally, providing a suitable environment and atmosphere for women to practice sports away from pressures is crucial

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